

A Workflow Management System Guide

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Abstract

A workflow describes the entirety of processing steps in an analysis, such as employed in many fields of physics. Workflow management makes the dependencies between individual steps of a workflow and their computational requirements explicit, such that entire workflows can be executed in a stand-alone manner. Though the use of workflow management is widely recommended in the interest of transparency, reproducibility and data preservation, choosing among the large variety of available workflow management tools can be overwhelming. We compare selected workflow management tools concerning all relevant criteria and make recommendations for different use cases.

Keywords: workflow management, particle physics, hadron and nuclear physics, astrophysics

1 Introduction

The extraction of scientific results from data often requires many steps of data processing. Usually there is a script for each step and the analyzer has to make sure they are executed in the right order. This is error-prone and makes it difficult to reproduce results and preserve analyses. Moreover it requires considerable manual work, in particular if the entire processing chain or parts of it have to be rerun many times which is often the case for analyses in

particle physics, hadron and nuclear physics, or astrophysics. These problems are addressed by making dependencies between processing steps explicit with workflow management systems. They can automate the execution of processing steps and thus reduce the effort analyzers have to spend on the management of their workflows. Furthermore, workflow management capture the computational environments and requirements to make analyses stand-alone executables in the interest of transparency, reproducibility and data preservation.

As workflows are relevant in many areas, various technical solutions exist. For example, ref. [1] lists several of them. Given the large number of technical solutions it is hard to decide which of them should be chosen for which use case. This article discusses criteria for the assessment of workflow management systems in Section 2. The criteria are evaluated for a selected set of solutions in Section 3. The choice of system has to be made case by case as the relevance of criteria is use case dependent. Some recommendations for typical use cases are given in Section 4.

We here assess both **workflow management frameworks** (Luigi and Snakemake) which construct workflows, and **workflow management platforms** (Reana) that allow for additional tools to instantiate and run the workflows on remote clouds.

2 Evaluation Criteria

USER INTERFACE

- **Workflow language:** Is the definition of a workflow given in a custom or standard language?
- **Relation to analysis code:** Does the description of the workflow factorize from the analysis code or is it integrated in the analysis code? A tight integration can be beneficial if workflows are well defined and strongly coupled to the analysis code. A factorized approach provides more flexibility and is particularly useful to implement existing code, but may require synchronized changes of workflow definition and analysis code. Does the system support multiple languages?
- **Boilerplate code:** How much code is needed on average to include a step and its dependencies in a workflow?
- **Visualization and monitoring:** How can the dependency graph be visualized and the progress of execution be monitored? Can partial results be inspected?
- **Learning curve:** How much effort does a beginner have to invest to get a simple/complex workflow running?

FEATURES

- **Supported programming languages:** Is the system agnostic to the programming language used for the implementation of steps or does it only support specific ones?

- **Data formats:** Does the system support only specific input or output data formats? Does it have features for the inspection of specific data formats?
- **Dependency management:** Does the system support one-to-many, many-to-one, and many-to-many dependencies? Can dependencies be generated dynamically? Are conditional dependencies supported? Can loops be implemented?
- **Execution control:** Does it allow to pause and resume the execution? Can changes be applied during the execution? Can workflows be run top-down or up to specified target files? Can intermediate results be reused?
- **Error handling:** Does the system reliably detect error conditions in processing steps and what error handling/recovery strategies are supported?
- **Logging and provenance:** What means are provided to identify reasons for failures? Does the system keep track of when, where, and in which environment steps were executed and which output they produced?
- **Version control and archivability:** Are tools for version control and archivability implemented? Is external version control possible (e.g. using git)?
- **Scalability:** How easy or hard is it to change from a small test setup to a large production? Can steps be executed in parallel?

RESOURCE INTEGRATIONS

- **Software and Environment management:** How are dependencies of the analysis code on operating systems and external libraries handled?
- **Storage systems support:** What kind of storage systems/protocols for input and output data are supported?
- **Remote execution system support:** What kind of batch systems for the execution of steps are supported? To what level of detail can batch system slot requirements be specified?
- **Authentication and authorization mechanisms:** What mechanisms of authentication and authorization for the access to resources are supported?

INSTALLATION AND CONFIGURATION

- **Installation:** How easy or hard is the installation of the system? Does it require root access or certain tools?
- **Architecture:** Is it a single application or a client-server architecture? Is the execution correctly resumed if the (client) application is terminated and restarted later?
- **State management:** How does the system keep track of the state of execution of a workflow? In a *report based* system the state of execution is stored in a central report file. An advantage is that all information is at one place. It come with the risk that the report file may not reflect the true state. In a *target based* system the state is determined dynamically by checking for the output of processing steps. This avoid the problem of inconsistent information, but leads to a higher load on the systems that are queried for the state.

- **Portability:** Can a workflow easily be executed from different locations?

SUPPORT AND MANAGEMENT OF THE TOOL

- **Documentation:** What kind of documentation is provided and how useful is it?
- **Support:** Which communication channels or tools for support requests are provided? What is the response time and quality to support requests? Is there a large community support (e.g. on stackoverflow.com)? How likely is it to get support from a specific science community?
- **Tool developers:** Who are the developers of the system? Is it a single person, a small team, a large community, an institute, or a company?
- **History and project activity:** Since when does the project exist? How actively is it developed further? What is the frequency of commits or releases?
- **User community:** How large/diverse is the user community? Is the system an established solution in some communities?
- **Long term perspective:** How likely is that that the system is still actively supported in several years?
- **Lock-in:** How hard or easy is it to change to a different workflow management system?
- **License:** What is the license of the product?
- **Use in PUNCH:** In which research fields is the workflow management system used within particle, astro-, astroparticle, hadron and nuclear physics (PUNCH)?

3 Assessment of Selected Workflow Management Systems

3.1 Workflow management frameworks

Workflow management frameworks are used to construct workflows which automatize e.g. task dependencies and task scheduling. We here discuss the Luigi and Snakemake frameworks. The selection of reviewed workflow management frameworks is influenced by the authors' background and will be extended continuously.

For each framework, we implement a simple example workflow, covering the key features. It consists of three processing steps:

1. Generate a random seed and write it to file.
2. Use the random seed to generate a given number of random numbers and write them to file.
3. Concatenate the files with random numbers, generated by calls of step 2.

This example workflows illustrates the most important features of workflow management:

- Constructing processing steps and connecting them in a workflow.

Fig. 1 Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) and directory structure for simple workflow in Luigi.

- One-to-many and many-to-one dependencies, as well as steps without dependencies.
- Passing parameters to and between processing steps.
- Using shell commands as well as python scripts in individual processing steps.
- Defining the input and output directory and file structure.
- Demonstrating the available workflow visualization tools.
- Specifying computational requirements, constructing virtual environments and running individual processing steps in them.
- Executing the entire workflow in a stand-alone manner.

Luigi¹

Luigi is a workflow management framework initially designed for uses in industry, with extensive support for dynamic workflow visualization and remote execution. The dependency logic is decentralized in Python classes with integrated analysis code.

Figure 1 shows the example workflow implemented in a Luigi workflow. Task 1 generates a random seed. It is used by Task 2 to generate an amount of random numbers, specified by a Luigi parameter, inside a docker container spawned from a given image. Task 3 concatenates the outputs of the calls of Task 2. For shell commands, the subprocess library has to be called.

```

#luigi_workflow.py
import luigi
import subprocess, os
from luigi.contrib.docker_runner import DockerTask

class Task3(luigi.Task):
    def requires(self):
        return [Task2(NumberOfRandoms = 10), Task2(NumberOfRandoms = 5)]
    def output(self):
        return luigi.LocalTarget("final/finalResult.txt")
    def run(self):
        command = ["cat"]
        for input in self.input(): command.append(input.path)
        with self.output().open("w") as output:
            output.write(subprocess.check_output(command).decode())

class Task2(DockerTask):
    NumberOfRandoms = luigi.IntParameter()
    def requires(self):
        return Task1()
    def output(self):
  
```

¹<https://github.com/spotify/luigi/>

```

        return luigi.LocalTarget(f"intermediateResult_{self.NumberOfRandoms
                                }.txt")

    @property
    def binds(self):
        return [f"{os.getcwd()}/workdir"]

    @property
    def docker_url(self):
        return 'unix://var/run/docker.sock'

    @property
    def image(self):
        return "container:v1"

    @property
    def command(self):
        return f"python3 random_numbers.py {self.requires().output().path}
                {self.output().path} {self.
                NumberOfRandoms}"

class Task1(luigi.Task):
    def output(self):
        return luigi.LocalTarget("initial/initialResult.txt")
    def run(self):
        with self.output().open("w") as output:
            output.write("42")

if __name__ == "__main__":
    luigi.build([Task3()], workers=2, local_scheduler=True)

```

```

#random_numbers.py
import sys
import numpy

def generate_random_numbers(seed_file,output_file,NumberOfRandoms):
    with open(seed_file,"r") as seed:
        numpy.random.seed(int(seed.readlines()[0]))

    with open(output_file,"w") as output:
        for i in range(int(NumberOfRandoms)):
            output.write(f"{numpy.random.random()}\n")

generate_random_numbers(*sys.argv[1:])

```

We call the workflow from the command line using `luigi --module Task3 --workers 2 --local-scheduler` or from Python code using `python3 luigi_workflow.py`. The docker image is built from a Dockerfile (`docker build -t container:v1`) and bound to the working directory.

```

#Dockerfile
FROM python:3.8-slim-buster

RUN pip install --no-cache-dir --upgrade pip \
    && pip install --no-cache-dir numpy

RUN mkdir /workdir
WORKDIR /workdir

```

USER INTERFACE

- **Workflow language:** Python.
- **Relation to analysis code:** For each task, the analysis code is integrated into the workflow logic.
- **Boilerplate code:** Minimal. Variable values can be passed directly between tasks by employing Luigi parameters, with automatic handling of conversion

of Python types. Typically per task class: one function each for input, output and analysis code.

- **Visualization and monitoring:** Workflow monitoring via local scheduler or in *Central Scheduler*. The latter allows for excellent dynamic DAG visualization and optional dynamic status messages. Partial results can be inspected manually for running and completed tasks.
- **Learning curve:** Straight-forward setup of workflows that factorize into targets and tasks, which are expressed in Python classes with integrated analysis code. Analysis scripts need to be altered to accomodate workflow logic code.

FEATURES

- **Supported programming languages:** Python.
- **Data formats:** Any format. Tasks are marked as complete once output files are created and written successfully, without further inspection. Output directories are created automatically.
- **Dependency management:** Decentralized and integrated in analysis code. Task dependencies are explicit by requiring previous tasks. For dependency inspection, workflows can be run dryly without executing tasks. Support for one-to-many, many-to-one, and many-to-many dependencies. If the directed acyclic graph (DAG) cannot be fully built a priori, such as for dynamic and conditional dependencies, tasks can be yielded from within another task. Loops can be implemented by using task parameters.
- **Execution control:** Execution cannot be paused, but workflows can be run up to specified intermediate tasks, as well as top-down. Intermediate results are reused. Changes require a restart of the workflow. Workflows can be run from command line or Python code. Multiple tasks can be batched together and scheduled as one. Built-in functionality to solve the atomic write problem (e.g. creation of temporary directories and move commands). For easy customizability, extensive configuration files can be added. For each task, further resources can be specified. Tasks can be prioritised. Upon successful completion of a workflow, dedicated code can be executed (e.g. sending a completion message).
- **Error handling:** The workflow is marked as failed if individual tasks fail, unless multiple retries are required. Failed tasks are reported, along with their parameters and error messages produced during their execution, but (incomplete) output is not cleaned up. Built-in event system allows to register callbacks to events and trigger them for a specific task class (e.g. on success or failure of a task).
- **Logging and provenance:** *Central Scheduler* captures execution history of tasks. Luigi allows for the specification of log files with adjustable log level, limited provenance information.
- **Version control and archivability:** External version control possible.
- **Scalability:** Simple scalability. Number of so-called workers can be specified. For multiple workers, tasks will be automatically run in parallel,

whenever possible. No execution is transferred, i.e. workers schedule and execute all tasks. This may limit scalability eventually.

RESOURCE INTEGRATIONS

- **Software and environment management:** Docker containers can be run as tasks. Luigi analysis workflow² (law) provides extensive features for environment sandboxing on task level. Support within commercial cloud systems.
- **Storage systems support:** Target classes map to files on remote locations (e.g. via ssh or ftp, on the Apache Hadoop Distributed File System etc.).
- **Remote execution system support:** LSF batch system support. HTCondor and LHC Computing Grid support can be implemented (see e.g. b2luigi³ or law). Support for Jobs on Sun Grid Engine, Spark Jobs etc. Cloud execution support Kubernetes, Dropbox, Google Cloud, Salesforce, Amazon AWS Cloud etc. Extensive support for Apache Hadoop jobs and the Apache Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS). Tasks can be marked as local, suppressing a batch submission. No support for distribution of execution.
- **Authentication and authorization mechanisms:** Luigi allows to access environment variables, which may contain authentication tokens.

INSTALLATION AND CONFIGURATION

- **Installation:** Luigi can be easily installed from the Python Package Index (pip), without root access rights.
- **Architecture:** Single application. Upon restart, existing output files will be detected and corresponding tasks will no be re-run. Running batch jobs are automatically detected and not re-submitted.
- **State management:** Target based.
- **Portability:** Workflows can be executed from anywhere by pointing to the corresponding scripts, as long as file paths are correctly specified.

SUPPORT AND MANAGEMENT OF THE TOOL

- **Documentation:** Extensive documentation on official website. Open source code on Github.
- **Support:** Support on stackoverflow.com. Luigi was initially intended for Spotify but translates to many other industries.
- **Tool developers:** Spotify Group.
- **History and project activity:** Developed by and for the Spotify group, open sourced in 2012 and in active development (currently multiple new commits monthly).
- **User community:** Active community, frequently used by companies.
- **Long term perspective:** Good, given prevalence, active development and industrial use.

²<https://github.com/riga/law>

³<https://github.com/nils-braun/b2luigi>

Fig. 2 Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) and directory structure for simple workflow in Snakemake.

- **Lock-in:** Likely, since analysis code structure needs to be modified significantly to accommodate workflow logic and no support for other workflow management frameworks.
- **License:** Luigi is licensed by the Spotify Group.
- **Use in PUNCH:** CMS (Law), Belle II Experiment (b2luigi).

Snakemake⁴

Snakemake is a workflow management framework designed for uses in research, with extensive support for environment management and remote execution. It features a very simple Python-based syntax and accommodates shell commands and external scripts in multiple programming languages with minimal adaptations. Due to this and its support for other workflow management frameworks, lock-in is very unlikely. All workflow logic is centralized in the so-called *snakefile*, similar to a Make-file.

Figure 2 illustrates the implementation of the example workflow. Task 1 generates a random seed. It is used by Task 2 to generate random numbers, by calling a separate python script. Snakemake creates an environment for the script to run in, which includes the specified packages on any machine. This can be achieved via the integrated conda package manager and within a container spawnable from a given docker image. With each call of Task 2, we pass a wildcard parameter to the script, which specifies how many numbers are generated. Task 3 concatenates the outputs of the calls of Task 2.

```

#snakefile
rule Task3:
    input:
        "intermediate/intermediateResult_10.txt",
        "intermediate/intermediateResult_5.txt"
    output:
        "final/finalResult.txt"
    shell:
        "cat {input} > {output}"

rule Task2:
    input:
  
```

⁴<https://github.com/snakemake/snakemake>

```

    "initial/seed.txt"
output:
    "intermediate/intermediateResult_{NumberOfRandoms}.txt"
conda:
    "environment.yaml"
containerized:
    "container.sif"
params:
    current_NumberOfRandoms = lambda wildcards: int(wildcards.
                                                    NumberOfRandoms)

script:
    "python_script.py"

rule Task1:
    output:
        "initial/seed.txt"
    shell:
        "echo 42 > {output}"

```

```

#python_script.py
input_file = snakemake.input[0]
output_file = snakemake.output[0]
number_of_randoms = snakemake.params.current_NumberOfRandoms

import numpy
with open(input_file,"r") as input:
    numpy.random.seed(int(input.readlines()[0]))
with open(output_file,"w") as output:
    for i in range(number_of_randoms): output.write(f"{numpy.random.random
                                                    ()}\n")

```

```

#environment.yaml
name: environment
dependencies:
    - numpy

```

We call the workflow from the command line with `snakemake --cores 2 --use-singularity --use-conda`, where `cores` specifies the number of parallel CPU cores. Alternatively for supported cluster execution, use `snakemake --cluster qsub --jobs 2`.

USER INTERFACE

- **Workflow language:** Custom human readable Python-based language with additional syntax to define tasks and workflow specific properties.
- **Relation to analysis code:** The description of the workflow (*snakefile*) factorizes entirely from the analysis code (separate scripts).
- **Boilerplate code:** Minimal. Typically per task in *snakefile*: one line each for input, output, script or shell command and additional arguments. Minimal changes to separate scripts allow to pass arguments directly, which makes parsing code unnecessary.
- **Visualization and monitoring:** Built-in commands to print workflow visualization to file (option to print entirety of workflow or omit multiple calls of tasks). Dynamic workflow monitoring through panoptes⁵ server and terminal-printout, albeit no dynamic DAG. Partial results and log files can be inspected manually for running and completed tasks.

⁵<https://github.com/panoptes-organization/panoptes>

- **Learning curve:** Quick and straight-forward setup of workflows. So-called *snakefile* contains all workflow logic with all workflow tasks (called *rules*).

USER INTERFACE

- **Supported programming languages:** Separate scripts and shell commands can be called directly. Support for Shell, Python, R & R Markdown, Julia, Rust and Jupyter notebooks for interactive development.
- **Data formats:** Any format. Tasks are marked as complete once output files are created and written successfully. Output file inspection possible through non-emptiness and checksum compliance. Output directories are created automatically. Specified temporary output files are deleted once not needed anymore. Specified protected output files are write-protected. Alternatively, directories can be specified as outputs.
- **Dependency management:** Centralized. *Snakefile* contains inputs and outputs for all tasks, from which their dependencies are determined automatically and motivated in printout. Instead of via filenames, dependencies can also be required directly by referring to outputs of specific tasks. Ambiguities in dependencies (e.g. tasks with identical outputs) can be resolved by explicitly specifying the executing order for tasks. For dependency inspection, workflows can be run dryly without executing tasks. Support for one-to-many, many-to-one, and many-to-many dependencies. Dynamic and conditional dependencies can be implemented by marking tasks as checkpoints, for which the directed acyclic graph (DAG) is re-evaluated at run-time based on the output of previous tasks. Loops can be implemented by using wildcard parameters.
- **Execution control:** Execution cannot be paused, but workflows can be run up to specified intermediate outputs, as well as top-down. Intermediate results are reused, unless the user requires a re-run. Changes require a restart of the workflow. Execution flags can be stored in profiles. For easy customizability, parameters and initial input files can be specified in configuration file. Built-in functionality to benchmark tasks. For each task, the number of threads and further resources can be specified. Tasks can be prioritised. Upon successful completion of a workflow, dedicated code can be executed (e.g. sending a completion message).
- **Error handling:** The workflow is marked as failed if individual tasks fail, unless multiple retries are required. Failed tasks are reported, along with their parameters and error messages produced during their execution. (Incomplete) outputs of failed tasks are deleted automatically.
- **Logging and provenance:** Snakemake allows for the specification of log files for each task. Additionally global log files for each workflow execution are written, including the executed tasks with their parameters, timestamps and activated environments.
- **Version control and archivability:** Snakemake tracks the code that was used to create output files; Tasks can be re-run automatically for changes in corresponding code. External version control possible.

- **Scalability:** Simple scalability. Modularization in sub-workflows possible. Number of CPU cores can be specified. For multiple cores, tasks will be automatically run in parallel, whenever possible. Large workflows can be executed in batches. Support for scatter-gather workflows.

RESOURCE INTEGRATIONS

- **Software and environment management:** For fully reproducible workflows, software tools and libraries can be specified in isolated software environments (globally or for individual tasks). This can be achieved using the integrated conda package management or by running within a (docker) container spawned from a given image. Workflows can then be executed without additional prerequisites, while software packages are supplied automatically on any machine. Snakemake wrapper repository provides frequently used scripts.
- **Storage systems support:** Snakemake allows to retrieve and upload files from and to several remote locations (e.g. via ssh, http and commercial cloud services).
- **Remote execution system support:** LSF batch system support. HTCondor and LHC Computing Grid support can be implemented (e.g. analogous to b2luigi). Cluster execution support for cluster engines that support shell scripts and have access to a common filesystem, with extensive job properties. Support for Distributed Resource Management Application API (DRMAA) and Slurm. Tasks can be assigned to groups, which are submitted together to the same computing node. Tasks can be marked as local, suppressing a batch submission. Cloud execution support (Kubernetes via Google cloud engine, Google Cloud Life Sciences with GPUs, Tibenna on Amazon Web Services, GA4GH TES).
- **Authentication and authorization mechanisms:** Snakemake allows to access environment variables, which may contain authentication tokens.

INSTALLATION AND CONFIGURATION

- **Installation:** A full version of Snakemake can be easily installed using Conda and Mamba, without root access rights. Similarly, a minimal version depending only on bare necessities is available.
- **Architecture:** Single application. Upon restart, existing output files will be detected and corresponding tasks will no be re-run \Rightarrow *Exception:* If a task features input files with newer timestamps than the existing output files, it will be re-run.
- **State management:** Target based.
- **Portability:** Workflows can be executed from anywhere by pointing to the *snakefile*, as long as file paths are correctly specified. Tasks marked as *shadow rules* are run in isolated temporary directories. Workflows and their outputs can be chained.

SUPPORT AND MANAGEMENT OF THE TOOL

- **Documentation:** Excellent and extensive documentation on official website. Open source code on Github.
- **Support:** Extensive support on stackoverflow.com and discord. Snakemake was initially intended for uses in bio-informatics but translates to any research field.
- **System developers:** Small team of developers led by Dr. Johannes Köster (University of Duisburg-Essen, Germany).
- **History and project activity:** Snakemake exists since 2012 with ongoing active development (currently multiple new commits monthly).
- **User community:** Very active community with > 7 new citations per week.
- **Long term perspective:** Good, given prevalence and active development.
- **Lock-in:** No. Snakemake features built-in tools to export workflows to *Common Workflow Language*⁶ (CWL), which serves as comprehensive standard for workflow management frameworks. Furthermore, the execution of individual tasks can be handed over to other workflow management frameworks. Separate scripts are only minimally changed for integration into Snakemake.
- **License:** Snakemake is licensed under the MIT License with free permission to alter it in any way.
- **Use in PUNCH:** LHCb Experiment, Radioastronomy.

3.2 Workflow Management Platforms

Workflow Management Platforms help to containerize computational environments and to run workflows on remote computing clouds. The selection of reviewed workflow management platforms is influenced by the authors' background and will be extended continuously.

Snakemake workflows on the Reproducible research data analysis platform (Reana)⁷

Reana serves as a platform that provides workflow execution as a service and is agnostic to the utilized workflow framework. We here discuss the execution of snakemake workflows on Reana servers, for which not all previously mentioned features of snakemake are available.

Figure 3 illustrates the implementation of the example workflow. Task 1 generates a random seed. It is used by Task 2 to generate random numbers, by calling a separate python script. Since Reana does not allow to directly pass arguments to scripts (only `shell` directives are supported from snakemake), additional parsing code is necessary. With each call of Task 2, we pass a wildcard parameter to the script, which specifies how many numbers are generated. Task 3 concatenates the outputs of the calls of Task 2. Reana does not support the conda package management in Snakemake, but containers can be spawned from given images.

⁶<https://www.commonwl.org/>

⁷<https://github.com/reana/reana>

Fig. 3 Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) and directory structure for simple workflow in Reana.

```

#Snakefile
rule Task3:
    input:
        "intermediateResult_10.txt",
        "intermediateResult_5.txt"
    output:
        "finalResult.txt"
    shell:
        "cat {input} > {output}"

rule Task2:
    input:
        seed = "seed.txt",
        script = config["generate_randoms"]
    output:
        "intermediateResult_{NumberOfRandoms}.txt"
    shell:
        "python {input.script} {input.seed} {wildcards.NumberOfRandoms} {
            output}"

rule Task1:
    output:
        "seed.txt"
    shell:
        "echo 42 > {output}"
  
```

```

#inputs.yaml
generate_randoms: files/python_script.py
  
```

```

#reana-snakemake.yaml
inputs:
    directories:
        - files
    parameters:
        input: files/inputs.yaml
workflow:
    type: snakemake
    file: files/Snakefile
outputs:
    files:
        - finalResult.txt
  
```

```

#python_script.py
import numpy

import sys
input_file = str(sys.argv[1])
  
```

```

number_of_randoms = int(sys.argv[2])
output_file = str(sys.argv[3])

with open(input_file, "r") as input:
    numpy.random.seed(int(input.readlines()[0]))
with open(output_file, "w") as output:
    for i in range(number_of_randoms): output.write(f"{numpy.random.random
        ()}\n")

```

USER INTERFACE

- **Workflow language:** Simplistic built-in workflow management framework called Serial, which permits to run tasks only in a linear sequential manner (therefore not reviewed here). Support for Common Workflow Language, Yadage and Snakemake workflows.
- **Relation to analysis code:** Depending on chosen workflow language. For snakemake workflows, full factorization of workflow logic and analysis code.
- **Boilerplate code:** Yaml file to specify computing environment, e.g. workflow, workflow language, input and output files etc. For snakemake workflows, parameters cannot directly be passed to scripts and additional .yaml files and parsing code are required.
- **Visualization and monitoring:** Dynamic monitoring and static DAG visualization.
- **Learning curve:** Simple.

FEATURES

- **Supported programming languages:** Depending on chosen workflow language. Multiple for snakemake workflows, but scripts cannot be called directly and are instead invoked via shell commands.
- **Data formats:** Depending on chosen workflow language; generally any format.
- **Dependency management:** Depending on chosen workflow language. For snakemake, one-to-many, many-to-one, and many-to-many dependencies.
- **Execution control:** Workflows cannot be paused. Changes require a restart.
- **Error handling:** Each execution requires a new upload and runs in a clean environment.
- **Logging and provenance:** Individual log files for all tasks are accessible at run-time. For snakemake workflows, additional global log files for each workflow execution, including the executed tasks with their parameters, timestamps and activated environments. Benchmarking in reana report.
- **Version control and archivability:** Previously uploaded workflows are accessible on server.
- **Scalability:** Simple. Apart from the built-in Serial framework, all supported workflow management frameworks support parallel execution.

RESOURCE INTEGRATION

- **Software and environment management:** Workflows are executed in containerized environments on server.

- **Remote execution system support:** Support for HTCondor, Kubernetes and Slurm compute backends.
- **Storage systems support:** Support for GitLab, CVMFS, EOS and NFS storage systems.
- **Authentication and authorization mechanism:** Users are authenticated using private access tokens to upload workflows to server.

INSTALLATION AND CONFIGURATION

- **Installation:** Reana-client can be easily installed from the Python Package Index (pip), without root access rights. Server can be selected from Reana cluster or installed individually.
- **Architecture:** Client-server architecture. Once the workflow is uploaded, the execution cannot be terminated.
- **State management:** Target based.
- **Portability:** Workflows are executed on server.

SUPPORT AND MANAGEMENT OF THE TOOL

- **Documentation:** Sparse and incomplete documentation on the official website. Open source code on Github.
- **Support:** Reana forum, chat on Mattermost.
- **System developers:** Developed by CERN.
- **History and project activity:** Established in 2017. Active with multiple new commits per month.
- **User community:** Originally developed for high energy physics, but translates to any research field.
- **Long term perspective:** Good, given active development and support by CERN.
- **Lock-in:** Unlikely, due to support for different workflow management frameworks. However, e.g. snakemake workflows might need to be adjusted to bypass snakemake features that are not supported on Reana.
- **License:** CERN Copyright.
- **Use in PUNCH:** CERN

Criteria	Luigi	Snakemake	Snakemake on Reana
Interface	Python integrated minimal extensive intermediate	custom Python-based complete factorization minimal no dynamic DAG simple	Python-based complete factorization some no dynamic DAG simple
Features	Programming languages Data formats Dependency management Execution control Error handling, provenance, logging Version control and archivability Scalability	single any automatic extensive failed output remains external easy	multiple any automatic limited single-use clean environment external and internal easy
Resources	Environment management Storage systems support Remote execution support Authentication mechanism	extensive support extensive extensive environment variables	some support extensive extensive access tokens
Install	Installation Architecture State management Portability	conda, non-root single application target based easy	pip, non-root server target based easy
Support	Documentation Support System developers History and activity User community Long term perspective Lock-in License Use in PUNCH	extensive extensive academic team very active large good yes Spotify Group, free use CMS, Belle 2	incomplete satisfactory CERN less active significant acceptable no CERN CERN

4 Recommendations

Before looking at specific workflow management systems we would like to give the following general recommendations:

1. If your task does or will in future consist of more than three interdependent steps, use a workflow management system.
2. Check your requirements. Which workflow management system features are essential, nice to have, irrelevant for the task you want to solve.
3. Is there an established workflow management system in your community? If yes, check if it fulfill your requirements.

Any recommendations of specific tools will naturally depend on the selection of the reviewed workflow management systems, of which a large variety exists. The current selection is certainly influenced by the background of the authors. We explicitly welcome extensions of the comparison to more workflow systems.

When choosing a workflow management system, the relevance of the above criteria has to be assessed case by case. Also, a possible lock-in should be considered because requirements can change and may call for a change of the workflow management system. Of course, the prevalent use of a particular system in a specific research field may play a significant role.

Based on the criteria above, we recommend the use of Snakemake as workflow management system in research unless the general recommendations suggest something else. Snakemake comes with extensive support for environment management and remote execution. At the same time, it features a simple but powerful syntax that allows for a complete factorization of workflow logic and analysis code. Therefore, the implementation of existing analyses in a workflow is possible with minimal effort and lock-in is very unlikely. It supports multiple programming languages and Snakemake workflows can be run on the Reproducible Research Data Analysis Platform (Reana) for extended functionalities.

If extensive support for Apache Hadoop jobs is required, the use of Luigi as workflow management system is preferred.

5 Conclusions

The use of workflow management systems should become a standard in physics research in the interest of transparency, reproducibility and data preservation. This has also immediate advantages for the individual analyzer, because it reduces the risk of (undetected) mistakes and saves time and tedious labor if analyses or parts of it have to be rerun several times.

Many workflow systems with different features are available and the choice of a system can become overwhelming. We compared selected workflow management systems in regards of a number of criteria relevant in physics research, to help with the choice of workflow management.

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